

IMPLICATIONS OF DROUGHT SEVERITY AND FREQUENCY OF OCCURRENCE ON AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION IN JIGAWA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This research work titled “assess the implications of drought severity and frequency on agricultural production in Jigawa State, Nigeria.” seeks to examine the characteristics of rainfall, drought severity and frequency, crop production trends and assess the relationship between drought and crop yields in the study area. Thus, Normalized Rainfall Index was employed to determine drought severity and frequency in the study area. Similarly, standard deviation and mean were all used to examine rainfall and crop production characteristics, while, correlation coefficient was employed to examine the relationship between drought index and crop production in the study area. The results revealed decrease rainfall in the 1980s and 1990s ($y = -2.5864x + 898.51$), with an increasing annual rainfall at the rate of 0.0085% in recent years. It was also observed in the study area, different degree of drought severities (10years of moderate droughts; 6years of mild droughts and 3years of severe droughts) dominated the period under study, which have affected agricultural yields in the study area. Similarly, positive relationship were observed between drought index and agricultural production in the study area. Thus the study reveals that crop yields have a strong relationship with the amount, concentration and distribution of rainfall. However, it was recommended that there should be water harvesting technique by farmers in the study area, lifesaving irrigation system, applications of a more realistic approach to agriculture by the government among others.

1. Introduction

Drought occurs in virtually all climates. Unlike hurricanes which are easily identified and straight forward to classify in terms of wind speeds, droughts are much tougher to define. Drought is an insidious hazard on nature (National Drought Mitigation Centre [NDMC], (2022). Drought means different things to various people, depending on their specific interest (Abaje, Ati and Iguisi, 2021). It is often referred to as a “creeping phenomenon” and its impact vary from region to region (Larry, 2014). Drought can therefore be difficult for people to

understand. It is equally difficult to define (NDMC, 2022).

Thus, there is no agreed definition of drought. Specialists who have differing perspectives have suggested at least 150 different definitions (Wilhite, 2000). For instance according to U.S. National Weather Service [NWS], (2018), drought is “a period of abnormally dry weather which persists long enough to produce a serious hydrologic imbalance”. However, in the most general sense, drought originated from a deficiency of

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precipitation over an extended period of time – usually a season or more – resulting in a water shortage for some activity, group or environmental sector (NDMC, 2022). In addition, based on disciplinary perspectives and interest, the following drought types were identified: meteorological, agricultural, hydrological drought and socio-economic or famine droughts (Arvind, 2006). The frequency of occurrences of extreme weather events such as floods, hurricanes, blizzards, droughts and heat and cold waves experienced in different parts of the world in recent years and the devastating effects of these severe weather events on human lives and property as well as national economies, constitute the most important environmental problem that mankind faces (USAID, 2017). The effects of extreme weather events on crops will be either direct or indirect, or both (Gwary, 2006).

Extreme weather and climate events have attracted considerable attention in recent years because of the large losses of life as well as tremendous increase in economic losses caused by the extreme events (Easterling et al., 2000). Evidence shows that climate change is increasing rainfall variability and the frequency of extreme events such as drought, floods, and hurricanes (IPCC, 2007). Boko et al (2007) predicted that Africa is likely to warm across all seasons during this century with annual mean surface air temperatures expected to increase between 3°C and 4°C by 2099, roughly 1.5 times the average global temperatures. Projections in

East Africa suggest that increasing temperatures due to climate change will increase rainfall by 5-20 percent from December to February, and decrease rainfall by 5-10 percent from June to August by 2050 (IPCC, 2007). Fluctuations of climatic elements particularly rainfall in northern Nigeria is not new especially in the northwestern ecological zone which comprises the northern Guinea, and Sudan-Sahel ecological zones of West Africa (Abdulkarim, Oladipo and Balarabe, 2015).

Available literature on Nigeria shows the existence of spatial differences in the nature of disasters (Daura, 2014). While oil and gas pollution is largely a Niger Delta problem, drought and quelea birds infestation occur in the Northern States (National Emergency Management Agency, 2022). Literature has also shown that the Sahel and Sudan savanna are drought prone areas (Odekunle, 2010). Several studies in the Northern region have indicated that the onset in raining season is highly variable and unpredictable (Hassan and Abdulhameed, 2022). There is a relationship between crop yield and the amount of water available for the use of crops (Devaiah et al. 2021).

Thus, summary of number of drought occurrences by states in Nigeria between the last decades shows Jigawa is among the region of highest drought occurrences in the whole country (Ahmed and Murtala, 2023). Drought has an adverse impact on the Nigerian society and economy in many ways with Jigawa State in particular, notably agriculture, food production,

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water resources, health, energy, human settlement and societal relations (Abdulmalik, et al., 2021). The present study attempts to investigate the implications of drought severity and frequency of occurrence on agricultural production in Jigawa State. This is the thrust of this research proposal.

2. Statement of Research Problem

It is evident from literatures of drought occurrences across the six geographical zones of Nigeria that the North-West zone had the highest frequency of drought (Murtala, 2019). The challenges associated with climate change are not the same across the country. Vulnerability analysis demonstrates that states in the north experience higher degrees of vulnerability to climate change than those in the south (Federal Ministry of Environment, 2020). The Northwest is the most vulnerable.

A large proportion of grain crops are grown in states in northern Nigeria (Madu, 2016). The high vulnerability of states in the north to drought poses a serious threat to food security throughout the country (Madu, 2016). This decline is as a result of high incidence of pests and diseases, persistent drought, poor management and lack of good quality seed. Reports from agricultural dependent producing countries lend credence to this fact. Using literature data of between: 1980-2014, Stefani, Lixin and Pierre (2015) synthesized global droughts effects on food legume production. The study revealed that in many regions of the world, their agricultural production has been adversely

affected by drought. It is evident that recurrent drought has constrained agriculture in Africa (FAO, 2016). In north western Nigeria both rainfed and irrigation or 'fadama' farming are practiced (Ibrahim and Salisu, 2014).

However, to the best of our review, we have not found any study that has attempted to assess the implications of drought severity and frequency of occurrence on agricultural production in Jigawa State in recent years. This research therefore, aims at filling this gap with a focus on Jigawa State, Nigeria. Jigawa State was selected because based on National Agricultural Extension and Research Liaison Services [NAERLS, 2022) statistics; more communities in Jigawa State have been affected by drought. Thus, Jigawa State is extremely vulnerable to drought and it poses the greatest risk to agricultural production than any natural hazard in the state.

Thus, no firm and consistent policy exist on the implications of drought compared to policies already in place which have been shown to have numerous effects on agricultural production. Although, the level of these implications and severities needs to be unraveled. In view of this, expected results for this research is strategize to achieve two goals: the short-term goal was to analyze the temporal trends of rainfall; examine the yields of agricultural production; establish the relationship between agricultural yields and drought occurrence; his long-term goal will be to provide evidence-based information for the

Ministries of Education, Environment and Agriculture.

3. Objectives of the Study

The specific objectives of this research are to:

- i. analyze the temporal trends of rainfall in Jigawa state;
- ii. Determine the severity and frequency of drought occurrence in the study area; to examine temporal trend of agricultural yields since in the study area; and to establish the relationship between drought frequencies and yields of agriculture in the study area.

4. Literature Review

The frequency of drought occurrence is also highly variable from location to location and each droughts is unique in its intensity, duration, and spatial extent. An event may persist for a few months or for several years and, for some locations, for a decade or more. Another characteristic of drought that distinguishes it from other natural hazards is its spatial extent. Thus, it is common for a drought to occur on a large regional basis, affecting millions of people and many different (Shetty, 2016).

Drought ranks first among all natural hazards in terms of the number of people killed from 1900 to 2004, and Asia and Africa rank first among continents in terms of the number of drought affected peoples during the times (Below et al., 2017). However, some regions are more prone to drought disasters either because of an increased frequency or severity of the hazards drought. A precipitation deficiency will more easily turn into a disaster when pressure on exiting water

supplies is high and capacities for effectively preparing for and responding to the effects of drought are low. In developing countries, however, drought ranks as the single most common cause of severe food shortages and is regularly listed as cause in the majority of the food emergencies (FAO, 2020).

Although drought can affects entire or regions. They can also be extremely variable in the spatial and temporal dimension (De pauw, 2015). Furthermore, De pauw (2015) observed that drought can occur during time of the growing season (for instance, early season, mid-season and late season). As described by the National Drought Mitigation Center in the United States [NDMC] (2020) as the effects of drought produce a complex web of impacts that spans sectors of the economy and reaches well beyond the experiencing physical drought. This complexity exists because water is integral to our ability goods and provides service impacts are commonly referred to as direct or indirect. Reduced crop, rangeland, and forest productivity; increased fire hazard; reduced water levels; increased and wildlife morality rates; and damage to wildlife and fish habitat are a few examples of direct impacts. The consequences of these impacts illustrate indirect impacts. For example, a reduction in crop rangeland, and forest productivity may result in reduced tax income for farmers and agribusiness, increased prices for food and timber, unemployment, reduced tax revenues because of reduced expenditures, increased

crime, foreclosures on bank loans to farmers and business, migration and disaster relief programs direct or primary impact are usually bio physical. Conceptually speaking, the more removed the impacts from the cause, the more complex the link to the cause. In fact the web of impacts becomes so diffuse that it is very difficult to come up with financial estimates of damages (Knutson, Hayes and Phillips, 2018).

In summary, drought is complex natural hazard that can affect a variety of sectors at local and regional scales. It can occur during relatively

Table 1: Land Area of Jigawa State

State	Square kilometers
Jigawa	23,287

Source: Office of the Surveyor-General of Nigeria

Jigawa State shares borders with the Republic of Niger in the Northern part, Yobe to the Northeast, Kano and Katsina to the Western

Table 2: Total Population in the Study Area (1991 and 2006)

	1991	2006	2016	2022
State	Total	Total	Total	Total
Jigawa	2,875,525	4,361,002	5,828,200	7,499,100

Source: National Population Commission

short time span at any time of year, or last several seasons or years. The impacts of drought are just as varied, depending on local and national vulnerabilities and the option available to reduce drought risk.

5. Study Area

In terms of location, Jigawa State is located between Latitudes 11.00° N to 13.00° N and Longitudes 8.00° E and 10.15°E (Figure 1). The area so defined covers a land area approximately 23,287km².

part, and Bauchi to the East. The State have a total population of 7,499,100 (Based on 2022 projection by National Bureau of Statistics).

Figure 1: Map of Jigawa State

In the study area, constant elements such as relative humidity and rainfall are heavily relied on to differentiate between the season and climatic zones. Jigawa State experiences two air masses that influence its climate; the relatively warm and moist tropical Maritime mass which originates over the Atlantic Ocean and is associated with Southwest winds in Nigeria, and relatively cool, dry and relatively stable tropical continental air mass that originates from the Sahara Desert and is associated with the dry, cool and dusty North-East Trades (*harmattan*). The highest temperatures are experienced about April in Northern Nigeria.

Minimum temperatures are usually in December. Maximum temperature could be as much as 40.6°C while the minimum could be as little as 12.8°C (Murtala and Abdulkadir, 2023).

5.0 MATERIALS AND METHODS

5.1 Data Required and Sources

The research was based on secondary source of data. Monthly rainfall data for the period of 44 years (1981-2024) was obtained from the archive of Nigeria Meteorological Agency (NiMet). This data was used because it is a synoptic station in the drought prone region of the State (Table 1).

Table 3: Data Required and Sources

Types of Data	Source	Data Description	Periods	Purpose
Rainfall	NiMets [Abuja]; NASA/Power Source Native Resolution	Monthly and Annual Rainfall	1981 – 2024	Temporal Trends, Drought severity and drought's

Agricultural Yield (Cowpea; Rice; Sorghum and Millet)	National Agricultural Extension and Research Liason Services	Annual Productions	Crop	2006-2024	frequency of occurrence Yields trends, Relationships with drought
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Source: Fieldwork (2025)

5.2. Population of the Study

The population of the study will comprise selected farmer in the state. A sample of 0.4% of the total population of the study will be taken, and distributed equally among the 27 Local Government Areas.

5.3. Sample and Sampling Technique

A purposive random sampling technique will be used to select farmers from each Local Government. Twenty five farmers from each local Government will be selected using systematic random sampling.

$$A_{sy} = \frac{R_{sy} - \bar{R}_s}{S_s}$$

-----eq... 1

Where: R_{sy} = the rainfall total for the stations during a year (or a season).

5.6 Trend of Rainfall

The standardized coefficients of Skewness (Z_1) and Kurtosis (Z_2) statistics as defined by [Brazel and Balling, 1986] will be used to test for the normality in the seasonal (May to October) rainfall for of the station. The standardized coefficient of Skewness (Z_1) will be calculated using:

5.4. Sample size

Twenty five farmers will be selected from each local governments both purposive and systematic random sampling.

The total sample size will be 675.

5.5. Drought Severity and Frequency of Occurrence:

Normalized Rainfall Index (NRI): This method measures severity and frequency of drought using annual or seasonal rainfall totals and the standard deviation to indicate the shortage of water of any given season. The normalized rainfall index for a given station as defined by Turkes, Koc and Saris (2009) was computed as:

The standardized coefficients of Skewness (Z_1) and Kurtosis (Z_2) statistics as defined by [Brazel and Balling, 1986] will be used to test for the normality in the seasonal (May to October) rainfall for of the station. The standardized coefficient of Skewness (Z_1) will be calculated using:

$$Z_1 = \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^{3/N}}{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^{2/N}} \right)^{1/2} \right] / (6/N)^{1/2} \dots\dots\dots \text{eq. 2}$$

And the standardized coefficient of Kurtosis (Z_2) will be determined through:

$$Z_2 = \left[\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^{4/N}}{\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^{2/N}} \right)^2 \right] - 3 / (24/N)^{1/2} \dots\dots\dots \text{eq. 3}$$

Where, \bar{x} is the long term mean of x_i values, and N is the number of years in the sample. If the absolute value of Z_1 or Z_2 is greater than 1.96, a Similarly, linear regression will be used to determine the linear trends of the rainfall for the station. It will be computed by using:

$$y = a + bx \dots\dots\dots \text{eq.... 4}$$

Where, a the intercept of the regression line on the y-axis; b is the slope of the regression line.

$$a = \frac{\sum y - b(\sum x)}{n} \dots\dots\dots \text{eq..... 5}$$

$$b = \frac{n(\sum xy) - (\sum x)(\sum y)}{n(\sum x^2) - (\sum x)^2} \dots\dots\dots \text{eq..... 6}$$

In applying Cramer's test, the mean (\bar{x}), and the standard deviation (δ), will be calculated for the station in the study area for the total number of years (N). The purpose of this statistic will be

$$t_k = \left(\frac{n(N-2)}{N - n(1 + \tau_k^2)} \right)^{1/2} \tau_k \dots\dots\dots \text{eq. 7}$$

Where, τ_k is a standardized measure of the difference between means given as:

$$\tau_k = \frac{\bar{x}k - \bar{x}}{\delta} \dots\dots\dots \text{eq. 8}$$

Where, $\bar{x}k$ is the mean of the sub-period of n -years. \bar{x} and δ are the mean and standard deviation, and t_k is the value of the student t -distribution with $N-2$ degrees of freedom. This

significant deviation from the normal curve will be indicated at 95% confidence level.

The values of a and b can be obtained from the following equations:

to measure the difference in terms of a moving t -statistic, between the mean ($\bar{x}k$), successive n -year period and the mean (\bar{x}) for the entire period. The t -statistic will be computed as:

will then be tested against the "students" t -distribution table at 95% confidence level appropriate to a two-tailed form of test. When, t_k is outside the bounds of the two-tailed probability of the Gaussian distribution (equal

to 1.96 at 95% confidence level), a significant shift from the mean will be assumed.

5.6. Measures of Relationship between Drought indicators and Crop productions

The relationship between rainfall and crop yield has been a subject of longstanding interest (Gote, Khodiar, Sadhu and Shekhar, 2010). Rainfall is the most significant climatic factor affecting agricultural yield as 70% of the crop

$$r = \frac{\sum (x-x)(y-y)}{\sqrt{\sum(x-x)^2(y-y)^2}}$$

r = Correlation coefficient

Where, x and y = individual observations of dependent and independent variables respectively

The agricultural yields values were used as dependent variables and rainfall value as the independent variable. This has been used in

5.7 Validity

The standardized coefficient of Skewness (Z₁) will be calculated using:

$$Z_1 = \left[\frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^3 / N \right)}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2 / N \right)^{3/2}} \right] / \left(\frac{6}{N} \right)^{1/2} \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. 1}$$

And, the standardized coefficient of Kurtosis (Z₂) will be determined as:

$$Z_2 = \left[\frac{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^4 / N \right)}{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N (x_i - \bar{x})^2 / N \right)^2} \right] - 3 / \left(\frac{24}{N} \right)^{1/2} \dots \dots \dots \text{eq. 2}$$

Where, \bar{x} is the long term mean of x_i values, and N is the number of years in the sample. If the absolute value of Z₁ or Z₂ is greater than

5.8 Structured Questionnaire

This was administered to assess personal views from the farmers on knowledge, attitudes, and practices concerning the implications of drought.

area is under semi-arid tropics characterized by low and erratic rainfall (Li, Cook, Gabella and Burch, 2010). Thus, the relationships between the rainfall value and the yield of cowpea, sorghum, rice and millet in the study area were tested using bivariate correlation analysis. This is represented as:

-----eq. 8

\bar{x} and y = Mean of dependent (x) and independent (y) variables respectively.

similar study on the relationship between rainfall and agricultural yields by Barrios, Ouattara and Strobl (2018).

1.96, a significant deviation from the normal curve is indicated at 95% confidence level.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

6.1 Validity

The results of the Standardized Coefficient of Skewness (Z₁) and Kurtosis (Z₂) for the station shows Z₁ and Z₂ of data for the station revealed

that the rainfall data of the station were normally distributed at 95% confidence level. Therefore, no transformation was made to the rainfall series.

6.2 Rainfall trends

Rainfall varies substantially yearly and over decades. Not only the amount but also the trends of rainfall can change and affect the

environment and society. Thus, the annual rainfall trends for Jigawa State was examined. Annual rainfall totals in Jigawa were analyzed to reveal their temporal patterns for the period under study (1981 – 2024). Figure 4 shows the graphical presentation of the annual rainfall trends for the Kaduna station smoothed out with 5-years Running Means.

Figure 2: Rainfall Trends and Fluctuations

In view of this, the linear trend lines for the station show a decreasing trend ($y = -2.5864x + 898.51$), indicating a normal condition. It is therefore clear from the results of the running Means and the linear trend line that the rainfall has been increase in recent years at 0.0085 percent per annum (in Study area). This finding agrees with previous study conducted by Easterling et al. (2000) that the long run of dry years since the early 1980s has been confirmed for the Northern Nigeria. In addition, Nicholson, Some and Kone (2000), attributed the decrease in precipitation values

during this periods to mainly drought of the 1980s. Besides, with regards to recent increase in rainfall studies by Ati, Stigter, Igusi and Afolayan (2009) lend credence to this fact that the late 1990s have been witnessing increasing annual rainfall totals.

6.3 Drought Severity and Frequency of Occurrence

The severity and frequency of the Drought Occurrence in Jigawa State Kaduna for the periods of 44 years (1981 – 2024) was 44 years (Table 4). As can be seen, it is quite obvious there was dominance of moderate drought,

which occurred for the periods of 10 years. Followed by 6 years of mild drought, and 3 years of severe droughts.

Table 4: Drought Severity and Frequency

DROUGHT SEVERITY	FREQUENCY OF DROUGHT OCCURRENCE	NUMBER OF YEARS
Very Wet	2020; 2012	2
Moderate Wet	1988; 1991; 1992; 1993; 2022; 2024	6
Mildly Wet	1981; 1982; 1986; 1989; 1994; 1995; 1996; 2012.	9
Near Normal	1983; 1984; 1985; 1987; 1990; 1997; 2007; 2008.	8
Mild Drought	2000; 2009; 2011; 2014; 2017; 2019.	6
Moderate Drought	2001; 2002; 2003; 2005; 2006; 2010; 2013; 2015; 2016; 2018.	10
Severe Drought	1999; 2004; 2023.	3

Source: Fieldwork 2025

In addition, based on the years with drought's different frequencies, drought dominated 20years of the last 25years records in the study

area. Similarly, these drought heated the highest intensities in 1999, 2004 and 2023 (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Drought Severity and Frequency

It could be concluded particularly in this zone that the occurrence of droughts in this zone already has a long history, which is not likely to disappear in the near future. These findings agrees with the studies conducted by Imo and Ekponyong (2011) who observed that in the last 40 years, Nigeria has witnessed severe drought. Also study by Tarhule and Woo (1998) revealed recurrence, persistence and periodicity of droughts (in one form or the other) in Northwest zone of Nigeria. However, despite the increase rainfall witnessed in recent years in the study

area, this study differ from previous studies through its finding that some areas still experienced drought conditions despite the increase rainfall.

6.4 Agricultural Production Trends

Jigawa State was prominent for its production in millet, rice, cowpea and sorghum especially in the past decade. However, since then, there has been upward and downward trends in terms of their production, thus, Figure 4 buttress this in the study area.

Figure 4: Crop Production Trends in the Study area

The results in Figure 4 show upward trends of millets between: 2006, 2009 and 2010 and

downward trends in recent years 2021 to 2024 in the study area, while, the trends for rice and

cowpea have remarkably been on the increase in recent years compared to their records in the 2000s.

From the foregoing, the decline of millet yields in the study especially in the early 2000s coincided with the periods of drought experienced in 2001, 2002, 2003, 2005, 2006, 2010, 2013, 2015, 2016 and 2018 in the study area. This finding relates with previous studies conducted by Okorie (2003), Alatisé and Ikumawoyi (2007) that crop yield have dropped by about 60 Percent in the Northern Nigeria. Similarly, Iliya and Sakwah (2006) observed

Table 5: Summary of Relationship Results

CROP	R-SQUARE	P-VALUE	F	STANDARD ERROR	T-STATISTICS
Sorghum	0.006202	0.748599	0.106104	0.44016	0.325737
Rice	0.0120224	0.654968	0.206894	0.045202	0.454856
Millet	0.017591	0.588318	0.304398	0.054145	0.55172
Cowpea	0.149035	0.102568	0.977325	0.023664	0.725493

Significant at 95% confidence level

Source: Fieldwork 2025

The results of the bivariate correlations analysis in Table 5 revealed the values of F as: 0.106104; (Sorghum); 0.206894 (Rice); 0.304398 (Millet); and 0.977325 (Cowpea) with P- values of 0.748599 (Sorghum); 0.654968 (Rice); 0.588318 (Millet); and 0.102568 (Cowpea) which is not significant at the $\alpha = 0.05$. This indicates that the predictor variable are statistically significant from θ zero, and significant predictability of the drought occurrence rate by the model. Similarly, an examination of the t- ratios support this

that drought forced about 68 Percent of the farmers to replace most crops with grains such as millet believed to be early maturing and more resistant to aridity.

6.5 Relationship between Drought and Agricultural Production

Crop yields in the study area appear to be similarly influenced by drought during the study periods. The results of the correlation analysis of annual rainfall and yields of sorghum, rice, millet and cowpea for Jigawa State are shown in Table 5:

conclusion using $\alpha = 0.05$. The t- statistics for droughts are: 0.325737 (Sorghum); 0.454856 (Rice); 0.55172 (Millet) and 0.725493 (Cowpea) with an associated P – values of: 0.748599 (Sorghum); 0.654968 (Rice); 0.588318 (Millet); and 0.102568 (Cowpea). This information indicates that there is significant correlation between drought occurrence and yield of Sorghum, Rice, Millet and Cowpea.

In the same vein, the standard error of the estimate $Se = 0.044016$ (Sorghum); 0.045202 (Rice); 0.054145 (Millet) and 0.023664

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(Cowpea) which indicate approximately 2.4% (Cowpea); 4.5% (Sorghum and Rice) and 5.5% of the rainfall is with $\pm 0:06$. Besides, R^2 for this correlation analysis are 6%, 12% 17% and 49% respectively for Sorghum, Rice, Millet and Cowpea. This implies that, these percentages of crop yields were affected by drought within the study period. This indicates positive relationship between drought occurrence values and agricultural yields in Jigawa State. This positive nature of relationship indicated that agricultural yield exhibited significant degree of freedom from drought which is significant at the 0.05% level.

This result reveals an unmistakable contrast with previous research by, Nautiyal (1999) and Nnaji (1999) which shows relationships were negative. On the other hand, this finding was in agreement with conclusion drawn from, NAERLS (2022) and Stefani, Lixin and Pierre-Andre (2015) which shows relationships are positive. This could be attributed to: first, the drought occurrence values in the study area in recent years were dominated by mild and moderate droughts, also because drought experienced during the last decade did not remarkably impact on crop yields as likely factor for positive relationships in the study area. These classes of drought are not associated with high water deficit. Williams (2020) has shown that the effect of drought depends on growth stages, deficiency level and environmental changes during drought conditions. Secondly, farmer's interest to cultivate more of cowpea

that requires less fertilization and cowpea farming is becoming more profitable venture in recent years.

7.0 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Drought is part of the environment. It occurs in every part of the globe and adversely affects the lives of a large number of people, causing considerable damage to economies, the environment and property. It also affects countries or regions differently, having a greater impact on countries or regions with poor economic conditions. One of the negative feature is the most frequent source of this phenomenon has been attributed to the occurrence of long-term rainless periods.

Based on the foregoing, there are grounds to conclude that before ascribing annual variations of a particular crop to rainfall, it must be assumed that some other climatic and biophysical factors remain constant. In view of this, it could be concluded from these results that there are fluctuations in agricultural production in the study area. In conclusion, the frequency of droughts in the study area has since led to an unstable agricultural production. These shortage results from an abnormal reduction in yield, such that it is insufficient to meet the nutritional or economic needs of the community.

From the foregoing, the following recommendations should be employed for meaningful development in agricultural production in the study area;

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Irrigation Related Recommendations

(a) In rain fed agriculture, the frequency of occurrence and duration of dry spells have an important bearing on the growth of crops. Some crops are highly sensitive to moisture stress and wither away if the moisture is not depleted in time. This can lead to partial and in some cases total failure of the crop. A single irrigation at such critical times can save the crops from total failure. Thus, farmers should be enlightened about water harvesting technology. This involves collecting and storing major parts of rain fall so that a crop life-saving irrigation could be given.

Non-Irrigation Related Recommendations:

(b) There is need for the development of a comprehensive agricultural and climate policy that takes into account the mounting risks associated with crop production among farmers. Therefore, based on the outcome of this research, Government policies in this area should be based on recent rainfall trends.

(c) Drought in the study area re-occurs and unless a long-term perspective is adopted about it and measures are introduced, the shock and destruction that come with it will always be of concern, hence, there are need for longitudinal and response farming techniques. These techniques consist of introduction of various coping strategies, analysis of dates of onset of rains, followed by decisions of [when to plant, the spacing to use, when and if fertilizers should be applied, the thinning schedule to follow and deep seedling of seeds], authentic adoption of

the recommended policies. Therefore, government and non-governmental agencies, and authorities in the study area are advised to adopt these techniques.

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Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

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